

Women's Participation in the Adoption and Management of Agricultural Water-Saving Technologies

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Abstract

Water is a fundamental resource for agriculture, yet its availability is increasingly threatened by climate change, population growth, and unsustainable farming practices. To address these challenges, water-saving technologies such as drip irrigation, sprinklers, and rainwater harvesting have been widely promoted as solutions to enhance productivity while conserving water. However, the adoption and management of such technologies are not gender-neutral. Women, who play a role in agricultural labour and household water use, face structural barriers in terms of decision-making power, access to resources, and training opportunities. This qualitative study examines the participation of women in the adoption and management of water-saving technologies in rural agricultural households. The research explores women's roles, challenges, and contributions by analysing how gender norms and responsibilities shape technology use. Data was collected from 20 participants (10 men and 10 women) through semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, and questionnaires. The questionnaire focused on five areas: background information, adoption of technologies, participation and management, access and barriers, and perspectives and suggestions. Findings reveal that although men generally dominate formal decisions about adopting new technologies due to control over land and finances, women play a vital role in daily water management, maintain resources for irrigation systems, and monitor crop needs. Women's contributions are constrained by limited access to training, financial resource, and land ownership. Social and cultural norms further restrict their participation in formal decision-making. Nevertheless, women demonstrated resilience and innovation, including reusing household wastewater for irrigation and adjusting planting schedules according to water availability.

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